

ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE IMPROVEMENT OF COOLING SYSTEMS IN REACTIVE POWER COMPENSATION DEVICES USED IN RAILWAY ELECTRIC POWER SUPPLY

¹O.Z.Toirov¹, ²Sh.Sh.Azimov¹, ³Wei Yu²

^{1,2}Tashkent State Technical University

³School of Artificial Intelligence, Wuhan University, China

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Reactive power is understood as the power required solely to generate and maintain magnetic fields, and reactive power compensation is the process of reducing or balancing the reactive power generated in electric networks [1, 2].

As a result of the development of power electronics devices, the use of various nonlinear (nonlinear) loads (such as electric arc furnaces, electric locomotives, variable frequency drives controlling high-voltage large motors, GTOs, IGBTs, and other large high-power fully controllable devices) has led to frequent voltage fluctuations in the electrical network and deterioration of electric power quality, which, in turn, affects the normal operation of certain equipment [3].

Reactive power compensation can improve the quality of electric power in the electrical network, maintain voltage stability, reduce voltage fluctuations, increase long-distance transmission capacity, and decrease power losses. Many problems related to the power factor can be solved by properly managing reactive power [4].

Various technologies exist for reactive power compensation, such as synchronous condensers, static VAR compensators, and static synchronous compensators (STATCOM). Synchronous condensers were used to maintain voltage levels and ensure system stability under various loading conditions or emergency situations. However, currently, synchronous condensers are rarely used, as they require solid foundations and a large amount of startup and protection equipment. Nevertheless, the advantage of synchronous condensers is their ability to temporarily operate under overload conditions [5]. A single-phase diagram of a synchronous condenser connection is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Single-phase diagram of a synchronous condenser connected to the power grid.

Radiator material: aluminum or copper

Thermal analysis and optimal fan positioning using ANSYS, SolidWorks, or COMSOL.

Heat distribution is verified based on FEM (finite element method)

EFFICIENCY BENEFITS

Indicator	Liquid Cooling	Air Cooling
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Maintenance	Complex	Simple
Fault risk	High	Low
Energy efficiency	Medium	High (variable)
Adaptability to load	Low	Good (via PWM)
Overall service life	Limited	Longer

Based on this scientific and technical analysis, replacing the current liquid cooling system in the BTCBH-2000/10 YXJI4.2 thyristor valve with a forced air cooling system is fully justified from technical, energy efficiency, and operational perspectives. This change addresses current issues and supports stable operation of the reactive power compensation system.